

MODERN METHODS OF TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE IN COUNTRIES OF HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract: This article discusses advanced methods of foreign language teaching in higher education, modern trends in foreign language teaching, and a person-oriented approach to education as one of the main ways to achieve success in learning a foreign language.

Key words: simulation, modeling, language portfolio, blended learning, methodology.

Modern society needs educated, highly qualified personnel who are characterized by mobility, dynamism, constructiveness, cultural enlightenment, respect the traditions of their countries and peoples. In the conditions of the information society, knowledge and professional competence gain priority in human life. In order to be aware of the development of world science, politics, economy and culture, it is necessary to study the main sources in the language of the authors, therefore, the importance of a foreign language in the university increases and its relevance affects the content, tasks and dynamics of education.

Acceleration and modernization of education requires the introduction of such innovative technologies aimed at intellectually and emotionally creative education of a person.

The principles of variability announced in the educational system allow higher education institutions to choose the model of the pedagogical process, including copyright. In such conditions, the foreign language teacher offers a certain freedom in choosing teaching models and technologies, without which the modern educational process cannot be imagined. Innovative events create specific characteristics of the teacher's activity in modern conditions, determine the transition from the paradigm of knowledge to interactive teaching methods.

Traditional methods of teaching a foreign language involve the formation of knowledge in artificial situations, as a result of which future research does not see the connection of the studied subject with future professional activities.

The most effective tool for developing the mindset of future graduates is simulation. This approach provides simulation of professional activity, its typical and important features. Its use allows the formation of communication skills and abilities; development of the habit of independence and self-management, contributes to the real preparation of the student for future activities, helps to make lessons more lively, interesting and meaningful, allows the student to express his thoughts more and more often, it allows expressing feelings, thoughts, evaluation, that is, critical thinking.

Consider modern innovative methods of teaching a foreign language aimed at more effective personal development and adaptation (both social and professional) within the framework of modern fast-changing society.

One of the ways to activate and motivate students in the process of teaching foreign languages is the method of design (projects), in which the student independently plans, creates, defends his project, that is, actively joins the process of communicative activity. An educational project is a set of research, calculation, graphic and other types of research conducted independently by students in order to solve an important problem in a practical or theoretical way. The main

goals of the design methodology are: self-expression and self-improvement, increasing motivation for learning, forming cognitive interest; the ability to apply acquired skills and abilities in practice, to develop speech, to correctly and rationally present the studied material, to conduct controversial polemics; demonstrating the level of culture, education and social maturity.

The projects are different:

- ❖ *role plays, dramatization, dramatization.*
- ❖ *research (generalization of scientific knowledge, historical, professional, etc*
- ❖ *creative (essays, translations, scenarios, etc*
- ❖ *multimedia presentation.*

Design refers to active learning methods based on the student being faced with the solution of specific situational problems encountered in real life. At the current stage of foreign language teaching, active learning is definitely a priority. After all, effective management of learning and cognitive activity is possible only if it relies on the active mental activity of students.

The goal of the natural method of teaching is to achieve an average level of knowledge of a foreign language. The teacher never draws the audience's attention to mistakes in speech, because he believes that it can hinder the development of speaking skills.

The full physical reaction method is based on two main conditions. First, foreign language comprehension skills should precede the development of all other skills, as in young children. Secondly, the lesson is limited to the concepts of "here" and "now" and examples that are easily explained in the yazy-ke being studied. The student is not forced to speak until he feels that he is ready for it. The method is not intended to teach writing and typing.

A versatile method. Study materials are presented in long dialogues with subsequent exercises in the form of questions and answers. However, the teacher's role here limits the possibility of creative use of the studied material by students in direct contact with each other.

Teaching a foreign language using the Internet. Today, the prospects for using Internet technologies are wide enough. This may include: email correspondence with residents of English-speaking countries; participation in international Internet conferences, seminars and other similar network projects; creation and networking of sites and presentations - they can be created jointly by the teacher and the student. In addition, presentations between teachers from different countries are possible.

Pedagogical experience shows that works on creating Internet resources are interesting for students because of their novelty, relevance, and creativity. Organizing students' cognitive activities in small groups allows everyone to show their activity.

However, it should be noted that information technologies and Internet technologies are not a cure for increasing students' motivation and independence in the cognitive process of learning a foreign language. In order to achieve maximum effectiveness, a wide range of innovative, including, of course, various media educational technologies should be used in the educational process.

Language portfolio as one of the promising tools of foreign language teaching. In modern conditions, a language portfolio is defined as a set of working materials that reflect a certain experience/result of a student's learning activities in foreign language acquisition. This collection of materials gives the student and the teacher the opportunity to analyze and

evaluate the scope of the educational work and the scope of the student's achievements in the field of learning the language and culture of a foreign language based on the results of the educational activities presented in the language portfolio.

Another innovative way of teaching a foreign language is blended learning. Educational researchers, teachers and methodologists are actively working on improving the process of knowledge transfer, acquisition and assimilation. The eLearning model is still imperfect and traditional education is no longer very relevant. Perhaps the truth in blended learning. It is an educational concept in which the student/student learns independently and personally with the teacher. This approach allows you to control the time, place, pace and way of learning the material. Mixed education allows combining traditional methods and modern technologies.

Advantages of Blended Learning. Proponents cite two major educational advantages of this approach: the ability to collect information and the alignment of knowledge and assessments. A third advantage of blended learning is that one teacher can teach many people at the same time. Blended learning allows teachers to reallocate resources and improve academic performance. This assumption was successfully tested in the Rocketship Education school network in San Jose, America. Among the advantages of blended learning, the following are highlighted: the introduction of asynchronous Internet communication technology into "live" educational courses helps to obtain an independent and joint learning experience at the same time. The use of information and communication technologies improves the attitude to learning, as well as the quality of communication between students / students and teachers. If we talk about specific topics, then blended learning is considered to be especially effective in teaching foreign languages, because it meets the need for live communication, online reading, watching videos, visualizing words. memorization", creates a game moment and interactivity that helps memorization.

Disadvantages of blended learning are the other side of this approach. This is uneven dog literacy, dependence on technology, broadband Internet, stability of online mode and unlimited tariffs. Often, the barrier to implementing this approach is low technology adoption, so teachers and students need to learn to work with a technology curriculum as well as a school blending platform. Another "inhibiting" factor is that training requires technical support and certain costs for creating video materials, training programs and test modules.

The task of developing, improving, and optimizing foreign language teaching methods has always been one of the urgent problems of Russian education. Studies of pedagogical work in this field have shown that teaching foreign languages in universities today is impossible without an innovative component. The status of the student and the teacher is changing in view of the modern requirements for the goals of foreign language teaching, they are moving from the "teacher-student" scheme to the technology of person-oriented teaching with close cooperation.

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